

Research Article

Aqua Guard Survival (A.G.S)

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Abstract: To address the worrying incidence of drowning, especially among children and adolescents in low- and middle-income nations, this article describes the invention of an inventive survival swimming kit. An enhanced safety feature kit with a tracking beacon for emergency locations, an aerogel-floating swimsuit, and SOS emergency food rations are included because drowning is a major cause of death in this age group. The aerogel increases swimmer safety in a variety of aquatic situations by providing better buoyancy and thermal protection than conventional materials. The emergency food supplies make sure that people who become trapped in the open ocean can stay energized until aid arrives, and the tracking device gives real-time location data that greatly enhances rescue operations. Overall, the development of the plankton database is consistent with the Sustainable Development Goals established by the United Nations SDG 14: "Life below water", SDG 3: "Good health and well-being," and SDG 13: "Climate action".

Keywords: Drowning, Flotation device, Safety, Sustainable, Tacking beacon.

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1. INTRODUCTION

According to the World Health Organization, drowning constitutes one of the top 10 causes of death for children aged 5 to 14 years old, with an estimated 236,000 people drowning each year. In low and middle-income nations, rivers, lakes, wells, domestic water storage vessels and swimming pools account for over 90% of drowning deaths; children and adolescents are rural regions are

disproportionately impacted ("World drowning prevention day," n.d.). Specific demographics are at a higher danger for drowning, notably children, especially males aged 1 to 14, and those participating in high-risk activities such as swimming, boating, or diving. Contributors to drowning events encompass insufficient swimming proficiency, poor oversight, alcohol intake, and already present medical illnesses such as epilepsy or cardiovascular disorders. The creation of this survival swimming equipment works as an initiative for decreasing the incidence of drowning among individuals. This new invention of the swimming suit also seems to be more convenient to swimmers as the floatation device is made to be portable size and already built-in the swim suit which solves the problem of the need to carry large size floatation devices and ready to use in the moment of any accident happen. This survival kit was known as Aqua Guard Survival (A.G.S).

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The utilization of aerogel as a floating tool turns into a lot of benefits compared to the conventional closed-cell foams utilized in floating devices mainly because of its even lighter specific mass and other characteristics such as high porosity and high buoyancy besides its excellent feature of thermal insulating. Therefore, Aerogel has an advantage of buoyancy and thermal protection that makes it superior especially for special purposes whereby these characteristics are quite useful (Long et al., 2018). Figure 1 and Table 1 show the sketch and part of AGS.

Figure 1. The figure above shows the sketch of AGS

Table 1. This table shows part of AGS's product

Technology	Current	Improvement
Emergency supply	None	SOS Emergency food rations
Floatation material	Closed-cell foam	Aerogel
Tracking device	None	Beacon

Some of the benefits of having a beacon as an emergency tracking device include real-time tracking location which is very crucial in enhancing the rescue team response time since they get accurate coordinates. Beacons are also relatively easy to use and typically maintain dependable and can be used in harsh environments and should be used to enhance safety gears. However, it has its disadvantages and some of the common challenges which are associated with the above devices include

Cost: Because the batteries are rechargeable, they require frequent maintenance such as battery check-up and battery replacement which make the overall price and structure too complicated. Also, at times, the signal from the mouse may be hindered for example by foliage or deep water and as such be helpful (Lin & Lin, 2018).

The presence of SOS emergency food rations in flotation devices is essential to the survival of individuals in open water as it provides for source of energy when one is stranded in open water, isolated for an indefinite amount of time. These rations are special cared nutrient provisions aimed at providing the needed amounts of calories and nutrients within, which is crucial for physical and mental activities under severe environmental conditions. The physically compact and non-thirst-provoking construct of SOS rations is advantageous for use in oceanic conditions where water and space are limited. Furthermore, they have long shelf lives, therefore increasing the probability of the reagents being available when rescue comes along (Jayaraman, 1984). Figure 2 shows the method before and after using the AGS.

Figure 2. The flow above shows the method before and after using the AGS

3. FINDINGS

3.1 People who are interested in water activities but have zero knowledge of basic swimming

Individuals without swimming proficiency who are interested in aquatic activities encounter considerable hazards, especially regarding safety and drowning prevention. Survival swim courses are tailored to impart critical skills that can avert drowning and improve water safety, emphasising self-rescue methods, breath control, panic management, and water safety knowledge. These courses prioritise instilling confidence via the establishment of a constructive learning atmosphere, incrementally introducing participants to water, and promoting a culture of safety.

3.2 Disable people barriers involved in aquatic activities

Persons with disabilities encounter multiple obstacles when endeavouring to engage in aquatic activities, encompassing physical and environmental impediments such as insufficiently accessible facilities, transportation limitations, and inadequate staff support. Attitudinal barriers, such as preexisting beliefs regarding their capabilities and potential instances of discriminatory treatment, further complicate their engagement. In addition, the presence of communication barriers can impede individual awareness of the programs that are available to them and can also make it challenging for them to comprehend and follow instructions. Health and safety concerns, specifically about the risk of

drowning and the implementation of emergency protocols, present notable obstacles. Moreover, the scarcity of research on adapted aquatic practices hinders the progress of creating impactful programs. To effectively tackle these challenges, it is imperative to implement a wide range of measures aimed at enhancing accessibility, providing better training for staff members intensifying outreach efforts and promoting research initiatives. These collective endeavours will empower individuals with disabilities to fully partake in and derive maximum benefits from aquatic activities.

4. DISCUSSION

An important safety feature that improves a person's capacity to keep afloat in the water is a floating tool worn with a swimsuit. The floating tool is essential for providing buoyancy in emergency scenarios, like abrupt falls into the water, boating accidents, or instances where a person is too tired to swim. It lessens the chance of drowning by keeping the body in an elevated position. It can also save a person's life if they are hurt or lose consciousness since it keeps their head above water, enabling them to breathe until aid arrives. This extra security is crucial for water safety equipment since it is especially necessary in erratic water conditions.

In open waters such as the ocean or huge lakes, a tracking device worn as part of a swimsuit can be extremely valuable for safety purposes. If something goes wrong, you get lost, go too far, or find yourself in danger, it lets people know exactly where you are, such as lifeguards or rescue personnel. In an emergency, even if you're out of sight, it can assist rescuers to locate and get to you fast. For swimmers and their families, this additional layer of security can be life-saving and a source of comfort.

Having SOS emergency food in a swimsuit can be critical in survival scenarios, especially if you're trapped or lost in the sea for an extended duration. SOS emergency food is small, portable, and contains critical energy and minerals to keep you strong and alert. It can help reduce exhaustion and weakness, allowing you to keep your physical and mental strength while waiting for assistance. In chilly waters, it also provides warmth through the energy it produces, enhancing your chances of survival.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, incorporating aerogel flotation, tracking beacons, and SOS emergency food into swimsuits improves safety and survivability in open waters. These advances increase buoyancy, allow for faster rescues, and provide crucial nourishment, particularly for non-swimmers and those with disabilities, increasing confidence and accessibility in aquatic sports. Furthermore, these swimsuits can enhance the chances of survival, encouraging people to learn more about swimming either with zero knowledge or basic knowledge.

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